

Complex compounds of ions with d^8 and d^{10} electronic configuration with a new thioamide of the dibenzofuran series

A. Kriza^a, A. Reiss^{*b}, V. Muresan^b and S. Florea^b

^aFaculty of Chemistry, University of Bucharest, Dumbrava Rosie, 23, Romania

^bFaculty of Sciences, University of Craiova, A. I. Cuza, 13, Romania

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New complexes of bivalent Ni, Pd, Pt, Zn, Cd and Hg with 3-thionicotinoylaminodibenzofuran (TNADBF) are described. The complexes are found to be of $[MLCl_2]$ type and the thioamide acts as bidentate ligand using both sulphur and nitrogen atoms as donors in the formation of complexes.

The coordination chemistry of sulphur donor ligands is an active area of research. A great deal of attention in this area has been focussed on the complexes formed by transition metals with thioamides that act as bidentate ligands using both sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms¹.

Here, we report the preparation and characterisation of six complexes of Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with a new thioamide, 3-thionicotinoylaminodibenzofuran (TNADBF)².

Results and Discussion

The complexes obtained³ were microcrystalline coloured powders, whose melting points are higher than that of the pure thioamide. They are stable at room temperature and their solubility in common inorganic and organic solvents is medium. The elemental analyses of the metal complexes suggest the formulae $[MLCl_2]$, where M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II},

Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}; L = TNADBF.

Ir spectra of the complexes and the thioamide were analysed^{3,4} and the results are presented in Table 1. The bands observed in the electronic spectra of the three complexes and their assignments⁵ are presented in Table 2.

The molar conductivities of the complexes (1.05–1.27 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) showed that the compounds are non-electrolytes. This also confirms the proposed formulation of the complexes as being $[MLCl_2]$.

The analytical, physical and spectral data suggest the following structure for the complexes :

Table 1. Characteristic ir frequencies (cm^{-1}) of the ligand and complexes

Compd.	ν_{NH_2}	δ_{NH_2}	ν_{CN} coupling C-C	ν_{CN} coupling NH ₂	ν_{CS}	δ_{NH_2}	ν_{NCS}	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$
TNADBF	3452 3224	1601	1539 1453	1361	1212 1186	970 940	850 739 718	678
[Ni(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3444 3240	1600	1454	1352	1209 1189	962	739 716	656
[Pd(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3446 3065	1600	1456	1354	1199 1164	948	748 722	668
[Pt(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3441 3064	1601	1456	1355	1199 1162	955	749 722	676
[Zn(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3450 3200	1600	1468	1352	1212 1188	966	740 720	666
[Cd(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3420 3220	1600	1460	1358	1210 1178	958	745 722	674
[Hg(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	3440 3190	1600	1458	1350	1212 1182	956	748 727	676

Table 2. Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the complexes

Compd.	ϵ_{max}	λ_{max}	Assignment
[Ni(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	160	21200	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	320	31300	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	9.470	40300	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\pi^*)]$
[Pd(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	180	16800	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	340	21200	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	6.700	33200	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
[Pt(TNADBF)Cl ₂]	190	17200	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	270	24000	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	7.000	34400	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$

Experimental

NiCl₂·2H₂O (Merck, p.a.) ethanolic solution (0.02 M), PdCl₂ (BDH, p.a.) ethanolic solution (0.02 M), K₂[PtCl₄] (BDH, p.a.) ethanolic solution (0.02 M), ZnCl₂ (BDH, p.a.) aqueous solution (0.02 M), CDCl₂ (BDH, p.a.) aqueous solution (0.02 M), HgCl₂ (Merck, p.a.) aqueous solution (0.02 M) and TNADBF (recrystallized) in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide solution (0.02 M) were used.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 Hewlett-Packard instrument and electronic spectra on a Zeiss-Jena spectrophotometer. The molar conductivities

of the complexes (0.001 M in DMF) were determined by using a OH-102 (Hungary) conductivity meter at 22°.

All the complexes were prepared by the reported method³.

General procedure: A solution of the thioamide (TNADBF) in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide was added dropwise with continuous stirring to an ethanolic or aqueous solution of the respective metal dichloride in a 2 : 1 molar ratio. It was gently stirred for 1 h and then left at room temperature for 3 h. The resulting metal complexes were washed with ethanol and diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure.

References

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